

Academic Review in Comparison with the Past of Reflexology in Modern Technology Applications

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Abstract

Applying pressure to certain reflex points on the hands and feet can have beneficial effects on the health of other parts of the body connected to these areas. Reflexology is a type of systematic body work. Each pressure points acts as a sensor on the feet and hands and is more specifically connected to a separate part of the body. Using the reflexology method will create a feeling of relaxation, increased blood and energy circulation, and help maintain homeostasis. This will be accomplished by stimulating the sensors located in the feet and hands. Reflexology sessions can be made more beneficial by adding a variety of therapies and treatments such as aromatherapy, relaxing music, and relaxed environments. In the field of reflexology, there is a technique known as reflex zone therapy. In the reflex zone treatment process, the patient's body is divided into ten separate zones extending from head to toe. In reflex zone therapy, there are five zones on both sides of the body. Each zone extends down one arm, continues down the torso, and then one leg down until it aligns with a toe of the corresponding foot. In reflex zone therapy, practitioners usually choose the appropriate application method to achieve optimal efficacy and efficiency. According to reflexology maps, reflexology is not an alternative therapy, but a complementary therapy to the various therapies the patient is currently taking. Complementary therapies are used in many areas of palliative care today, either to alleviate a problem without addressing the underlying cause or to improve the emotional, physiological, and mental health of the patient to increase the value of his life. Complementary therapies are used today. The Rwo Shur technique and the Ingham reflexology method are two globally accepted approaches to practice. The first approach does not involve the use of any tools or tools in its implementation, but the second way involves the use of tools and implements such as wooden sticks. There are five different schools of thought that explain how reflexology can improve a person's overall body health.

Keywords: *Reflexology, Reflexology Applications, History of Reflexology, Side Effects of Reflexology*

1. Introduction

There is a connection between the first and second fundamental theories and energy. According to the energy theory, different parts of the body can interact with each other through electromagnetic fields and this communication can be disrupted depending on the environment. The third and fourth theories both suggest that energy flow can be restored, while the fourth theory focuses on the possibility that a currently closed channel can be unblocked. The last idea suggests that reflexology can dissolve the lactic acid crystal that usually forms in the foot, thereby facilitating the free passage of energy through the body.

2. Beginning to Use the Modern Reflexology Technique for the First Time

It has been sixty years since the modern reflexology technique was first introduced, and since then, an increasing amount of scientific and clinical research has been conducted due to the positive effects of these techniques in reducing and relieving symptoms associated with various diseases. Certain demographics of individuals can benefit from reflexology, and the practice usually has no adverse side effects if patients with certain medical conditions take appropriate precautions before seeking treatment. Because everyone's body systems have a unique situation, the effects of reflexology therapy can vary from patient to patient.

According to the latest research, reflexology appears to be beneficial in helping body systems restore their original state.

The extent to which reflexology is successful in relieving the symptoms of various disorders is currently one of the most debated topics in the field. Patients undergoing reflexology treatment see a reduction in the severity of their illness as well as their discomfort. According to the findings of a study conducted in Switzerland, a significant decrease in the amount of medication required was seen in patients participating in reflexology sessions.

Reflexology, which is considered a complementary therapy, appears to be more effective in the treatment of some ailments when combined with conventional therapy. The most important ongoing discussions in the field of reflexology are those that focus on health, safety, and cleanliness. Furthermore, ensuring the reliability of administering this therapy requires an understanding of the underlying fundamentals of reflexology as a type of complementary therapy and the procedures involved in the treatment itself.

3. An Overview of the History of Reflexology

Based on observations of many aspects of Egyptian daily life, including medical procedures, the ancient Egyptians are credited with making the first discovery of reflexology.

Other studies have reported that reflexology originated in China over the last 5,000 years; however, no documents were found; therefore, reflexology is considered a part of Egyptian culture since 2330 BC, with a hieroglyphic wall painting inside the pyramid found at Saggara .

By the end of the 14th century, a type of treatment like reflexology, known as zone therapy in Europe, was already in use. Considered the father of modern reflexology, Dr. William Fitzgerald (1872–1942) discovered that area therapy was used by Aboriginal Americans. Raised among Native American tribes in North America, Jenny Wallace learned that applying pressure to the soles of her feet was one of the reasons for the healing process. The results of the Fitzgerald research contributed to the widespread adoption of reflexology in the United States. The realization that pain can be relieved by pressure applied to the hands, nose, ears and many other areas led to the development of zone therapy. Working in Washington, Dr. Joe Shelby Riley has devoted a great deal of time and energy to researching many forms of therapy, including reflexology, and has done so for many years. Eunice Ingham (1879–1974), Dr. She worked with Riley as a therapist and contributed significantly to efforts to educate people about reflexology. 8 With publications such as *Stories Told by Feet*, *Stories Told by Feet*, *Stories Told by Feet*, he brought the reflexology treatment method to wider masses. The publication of another prominent lady in the field of

therapy with her 500,000-selling book "Helping Foot Reflexology" contributed to the increase in the popularity of reflexology.

4. Benefits of Reflexology

Because of its high degree of safety and effectiveness, reflexology is the treatment of choice for most individuals seeking to improve their overall body health. It is very simple to use and provides a natural treatment that does not require the use of any medication. Learning and using reflexology are extremely simple and there are no restrictions on when and where individuals can practice it. Reflexology can be used whenever and wherever people want . It can lead to a variety of health benefits, including its effectiveness in treating the underlying causes of certain diseases, helping to relieve the stresses of everyday life, and easing the consequences of illness and injury. On the other hand, it is not used in the diagnostic procedure.

It is estimated that stress is responsible for 80 percent of the development of any disorder. The remaining 20% of stress will affect other ailments. One of the many advantages that reflexology offers is the reduction of tension. This is accomplished by applying pressure to a specific place on the hands and feet. This has the potential to provide general relaxation while simultaneously relaxing the targeted area . One way to disrupt the repetitive stress pattern those individuals often experience as a result of their lifestyle is the practice of reflexology. They will function more effectively after a series of reflexology sessions. This is since the first application will interrupt the stress response mechanism, and subsequent applications will improve the condition of the body. In addition, reflexology allows the body to relax and unwind from the stresses of daily life.

Pain is a source of stress in the body system, and if an injury occurs in any part of the body, the entire system is strained as a result. As a result of taking reflexology, endorphins, a substance naturally found in the body that relieve pain, will be produced. Endorphins are responsible for teaching the body how to respond appropriately to any injury. Reflexology practitioners have a strong belief that method is responsible for healing injuries they have in their lives.

It is beneficial for the general health and well-being of the person on a physical, emotional and spiritual level and is normally improved as a result of its use.

People choose reflexology for this simple reason:

- *The therapy does not involve the use of any pharmaceuticals or chemicals and is adaptable to a wide variety of medical conditions.*
- *Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects.*
- *It helps the body maintain agility and mobility.*
- *It creates a general sense of relaxation, especially in overworked or tired hands, feet and other parts of the body.*
- *It promotes the release of molecules responsible for relieving pain in the body.*
- *As a preventive measure against any disease.*
- *It accelerates the recovery process, especially after an accident in any part of the hands or feet.*

The left side of the body is represented by a series of band reflex areas above the left hand, from the upper left side of the head to the knee. In particular, the reflex zone including the lymph nodes, inguinal and fallopian tubes was surrounding the wrist.

The right side of the body can be represented by this reflex zone. There is an invisible point called the waist, located at the base of the long bones in the hand. This line marked the separation between the two halves of the hand. The reflex zone of the upper back is located above the line, while the reflex zones of the lower back, hips and internal organs are located below it. The left side of the body is associated with this reflex zone. The shoulder blades are located outside the body, and the reflex zone of the spine is inside. The fingers are the location of the head and neck reflex zone, while the area at wrist 1 contains the tailbone reflex area. The internal organs on the left and right sides of the body are different. (“Re: Why are the left and right lungs two different sizes? - MadSci”) (“Re: Why are the left and right lungs two different sizes? - MadSci”) Therefore, each reflex zone is uniquely associated with a particular organ. The right side of the body can be

represented by this reflex zone. For example, the reflex zone corresponding to the liver can only be found on the right side of the palm¹. The reflex zone of the spine is located on the inside of the upper part of the left foot, and the reflex zone of the shoulder is located on the outside. In a reflex zone, the lung, chest, chest, and back are grouped together.

This reflex zone is associated with the right side of the body, which includes the right arm and right leg. There is a waist in the middle of each foot. ¹ The lower part of the back and all organs connected to it are located under the line, the upper part of the back and all organs connected to it are above the line. ¹ Inguinal reflex and lymph node rotates around the ankle .

3. Treatment of Reflex Zones

The reflex zone is the area in zone therapy that shows how each part of the body connects to the rest of the body as a whole. When pressure is applied to this area, it will help a particular organ or part, which in turn will reduce the pain and symptoms of a disease. (“Revisiting reflexology: Concept, evidence, current practice, and ...”) (“Revisiting reflexology: Concept, evidence, current practice, and ...”) The theory proposes that instead of using reflexology maps, there is an unseen route traveling vertically over the body based on lines. According to this theory, each point on the soles of the hands and feet is associated with a specific organ.

Pituitary gland, pineal gland, brain, hypothalamus, thyroid , sinuses, larynx, nose, trachea, tongue, esophagus, thymus , heart, spine, pancreas, breast, small intestine and large intestine, as well as prostate.

4. Meridian Reflex Zone

The number of learning centers providing reflexology training is currently very limited. In most cases, an apprenticeship is the best way for someone interested in learning reflexology to acquire the necessary knowledge. There is also a facility known as the CEPP Health Center that offers five days of reflexology training courses. The instructors responsible for this intensive training program

are certified professional therapists from the UK's International Therapy Examination Council (ITEC), which also holds a diploma in aromatherapy and holistic massage. They are truly committed to helping participants achieve their certification goals. In this course we will cover various topics related to reflexology theory. Some of these topics include the anatomy of the feet, including bones and muscles, as well as reflex zones of the feet. Both theoretical and practical application will be covered in this course.

The ancient practice of reflexology served as the foundation for the development of modern reflexology. There is evidence that some form of foot and hand treatment was practiced in China as far back as 2330 BC, as well as in Egypt, as depicted in the tomb of Ankmahor . This technique was also applied in Egypt in the same period. It is believed that several Native American tribes in North America have practiced some form of foot treatment for hundreds or even thousands of years.

An automatic or instinctive action in response to a stimulus is what the dictionary means when it refers to a "reflex" , but the word can also be used to mean a reflection or mirror image. The reflexes found in our hands and feet are like mirror copies of the rest of our body. As early as 1500 AD, people were practicing zone therapy. It was stated that the former President of the USA, James Abram Garfield, relieved his pain by applying pressure to his feet.

Between 1915 and 1917, Dr. William Fitzgerald is credited with reinventing a form of systemic foot therapy and calling it Zone Therapy. During this time, he brought the concept to the attention of the medical community. An article titled "Pinch your toe to stop toothache" written by Edwin Bowers in 1915 is " Everybody's Magazine . This article marks the first time that Dr. Fitzgerald's work on Zone Therapy has been brought to public attention.

Historians believe that reflexology was practiced for a considerable time and dates to ancient times. No one knows who first started practicing reflexology. Both Western and Eastern influences were important in the creation of reflexology, and these influences can be seen in the beliefs, practices, and scientific foundations of reflexology used today.

Reflexology can be traced back to 2500 BC in ancient Egypt. (“WHAT IS REFLEXOLOGY? Reflexology can be traced back to 2500 BC”) (“WHAT IS REFLEXOLOGY? Reflexology can be traced back to 2500 BC”) There is evidence that reflexology may have been used in the ancient Egyptian papyrus, an ancient record. The papyrus depicts medical ancient Egyptian practitioners treating patients with hands and feet. This means that reflexology may have been used. Murals dating back to 2330 BC were unearthed by archaeologists working in Saqqara . These paintings were found in a tomb known as Ankhmahor that belonged to a physician. The paintings depicted individuals undergoing outpatient treatment.

There are other finds in China, Japan, and India, where stone sculptures showing ancient traditions of healing procedures such as feet have been unearthed. These discoveries were made in these countries. Historians believe that there was once a health resort in Greece known as "Delphi", which offered services such as massage, hydrotherapy and reflexology to its clients to promote relaxation and general wellness.

It is hypothesized that the fire that devastated the vast library at Alexandria may have led to the loss and destruction of a significant number of ancient strategies and records from ancient Greece, Egypt and the Near East. These methods may have been incorporated into the ancient art of reflexology. They may also have provided an in-depth demonstration of ancient manipulation techniques performed on the foot, including many types of ancient massage techniques. As a result, it is assumed that most ancient reflexology procedures and knowledge may have spread across Europe through oral teaching.

There is evidence that manipulative methods were used on foot in Europe during the Middle Ages (around the 14th century). These techniques were common in all social strata. It has been hypothesized that the Florentine Italian artist Cellini (1500-1571) may have used pressure manipulation methods on his hands and feet. These techniques may have helped reduce or relieve discomfort. As a result, there has been textual evidence implying that a book based on site therapy was produced by the doctors Adamus and A'tatis in 1582. The title of the book is said to be "Regional Therapy". This raises the possibility of using reflex and manipulation methods on the hands and feet of individuals in countries located in Central Europe at that time.

There is speculation that a German physiologist first used the term reflex in a book on motor responses in the body published in 1771. The idea for the head zone was developed in the UK by Sir Henry Head. According to the head area idea, certain areas of the skin can be affected by the internal components of the body through the neurological system.

In addition, Eunice D. Ingham founded the National Institute of Reflexology, traveling the world educating others about the therapeutic advantages of reflexology and mapping the entire human body in the hands and feet. He is known for pioneering the field of reflexology.

that a Swiss Catholic missionary named Father Joseph Eugster suffered from arthritis that did not respond well to Western medical treatments available at the time . In 1970, Father Joseph Eugster was sent to Taiwan to fulfill his missionary assignment. While in Taiwan, a colleague recommended that I go through regular reflexology treatments to relieve my arthritis and accompanying symptoms . It is assumed that Father Joseph Eugster's symptoms improved dramatically as a direct result of his participation in regular reflexology sessions. As a direct result of this, Father Joseph Eugster took an interest in the practice of reflexology and was later given a copy of a book entitled "Good Health for the Future" written by a Swiss nurse named Heidi Masafret . Father Joseph Eugster was a reflexology student and eventually passed on his knowledge to others interested in the practice. Father Joseph's popularity soared, eventually resulting in his television appearances.

During this time Joseph and Thonet The two brothers, named Tschen , were trained by Father Joseph and in 1982 Rwo They founded the Shur Institute. While Father Joseph Eugster continued his missionary work, his brothers continued the teachings and procedures of reflexology he developed. Integrating the ideas and practices of reflexology with Traditional Chinese Medicine, Rwo the Shur Method is named in honor of Father Joseph. The Father Joseph reflexology technique is said to be distinctive as it uses a greater amount of pressure than Western approaches. Father Joseph counseled patients to better withstand the pressure, as he felt that his approach healed the patient's ailments more quickly.

Since its founding in 1984, the Society of Reflexologists (AoR) has become widely recognized as the leading, aspirational and independent Professional Association for reflexology in the UK.

The Association of Reflexologists (AoR) is a non-profit organization that works with various outside organizations and advisory groups to help promote the highest possible standards in the reflexology profession. It also offers advice and direction to reflexologists .

5. Development of Reflexology

The development of reflexology of the feet as we know it today was finally created by the dedicated work of Eunice Ingham from the early 1930s until 1974, when she died. It is now known as the 'Mother of Reflexology'. Eunice found that the foot reflexes were the most responsive to stimuli and went on to create reflex charts that show how the body is mapped in the feet. He published ' Stories Feet Can Tell' in 1938 , later 'Stories That Feet Tell' in 1951, and finally ' Stories That Feet Tell ' in the 1960s . The term 'reflexology' originated in the 1960s when physiotherapists objected to the use of the word 'therapy' and after various other versions Reflexology stuck with ' -ology ' meaning science or the study of a subject or discipline . Mildred Carter worked with Fitzgerald and shared her techniques with Dr. Riley . He worked as a therapist in the 1950s, traveling the world to lecture on his theories. Eunice traveled around America, also giving seminars, and Ed Johnstone , Ena Campbell, and Laura Kennedy, who attended one of these seminars in Seattle , later took their new knowledge back to Canada. Eunice returns to England to find the Bayly School of Reflexology. Bayly and wrote ' Reflexology Today' in 1978 . Hanne from Germany Marquardt also learned with Eunice and expanded on the ideas by describing three transverse regions in the feet that reflect the three parts of the body:

head/neck/shoulder area, chest and upper abdomen and pelvic area of lower abdomen.

gave treatments to her ailing niece Dwight Byers . He continued his studies at the International Institute of Reflexology, which was established in Florida, USA in the 1970s. Today, there are schools all over the world where the art of Reflexology is taught and practiced using countless versions and methods. In the West, Eunice and others adopted and taught a rather heavy-handed technique using fingers and thumbs; this technique was later adapted by a therapist, Gladys Evans. Eastern techniques are known to be stronger with the use of knuckles and even tools like wooden

sticks, so they should be more aware of certain contraindications when giving treatment. Reflexology styles may differ from country to country and from therapist to therapist, but they all have the same goal: to relieve pain, relieve discomfort, and promote health and well-being. The extent to which these big brains are sized to support how pressing one part of the body has a therapeutic effect on another part of the body, which has conducted countless studies over many years, applying its knowledge and science, offers the confidence of Reflexology. Not only does it feel great, but it can achieve great results beyond the deep relaxation it instills in the beginning.

Throughout history, references have been made to working on feet, hands and ears in many civilizations. An early Egyptian tomb drawing depicts something resembling a modern-day Reflexology session, and the fact that it was found in the Physician's tomb seems genuinely relevant. The hieroglyphs read "Please don't hurt me" and the answer is "I will act so you can praise me".

Reflexologists believe that every part of your body is reflected in your feet and hands, and micro (miniature) versions of the macro (large) version can be found throughout the body, even in the ears!

Based on Zone Theory and then Reflexology, Zone Therapy hypothesizes that the body can be divided into 10 longitudinal zones, five on each side. Zone 1 will be the part from the big toe directly to the body. Any area of the body that is compressed within this region (among others Dr. William Fitzgerald and Dr. Joe Shelby According to Riley) it will affect all other regions in the region. ("A brief history of the origins of reflexology and where it is today ...") ("A brief history of the origins of reflexology and where it is today ...") Ear, nose and throat surgeon in the 1900s, Dr. "Squeeze your finger to stop this toothache," said an early article by Fitzgerald.

"Reflexology as we know it today began within the medical profession." ("A brief history of the origins of reflexology and where it is today ...") ("A brief history of the origins of reflexology and where it is today ...") Although deemed to work after substantial anecdotal evidence, Supplement

was not included in the industry because more money and less time was spent on prescribing a prescription.

At the time, money was not spent on scientific research, but these days more and more research projects are being undertaken to help confirm the effectiveness of Professional Reflexology Therapy. Here are some A-Z links to reflexology research trials.

While the exact beginnings of reflexology are uncertain, people from a wide variety of ancient civilizations and cultures used their hands, feet, and ears to treat a variety of ailments. This practice is now known as reflexology. A well-known example of this can be seen in a collection of Egyptian drawings discovered in a doctor's tomb. Until 2330, it was assumed that the Egyptians used some form of reflexology.

6. Other Parts of Your Body, Your Feet and Even Your Ears

Reflexology is based on the principle that your hands, feet, and even your ears can provide information about other parts of your body. This is the basic principle of the application. And the proof of this hypothesis is Zone , an early form of Reflexology dating back to 1500 AD. It can be found on Therapy . James A. Garfield, the 18th President of the United States, also used it because he discovered that putting pressure on his feet helped reduce the suffering he experienced. In the 16th century, many works were written on Zone Therapy and the effects of applying pressure to certain areas of the foot. These articles discussed the effects of applying pressure. " Everybody's " in 1915 Magazine published an article titled "Pinch your finger to relieve toothache". The article was written by Edwin Bowers and developed by Dr. Fitzgerald " Zone " It is based on a hypothesis on " Therapy ".

Anyone of any age and in almost any condition can benefit from reflexology. There are several programs that last between four and six weeks and can help relieve pain, cure or recover from illness.

Rahim Ariff Don, you should know that reflexology is getting a lot of attention these days. Because the treatment is so successful, many consider it a miracle. Many people are interested in learning more about it and putting it into practice. The author of this book has high expectations that he can meet these requirements. Also, the author of this book has high expectations that it will serve as a reference for dormitory reflexology. The emergence of today's homologous dimension sheds light on the symptoms hidden by the basic principles of reflexology. The words "reflection" and "reflection" are where the name "reflexology" comes from. These words mean "shadow" and "reflection" in English. The logical appendix indicates that it is also scientific research. Therefore, a more precise term like reflexology is used. Because of these mistakes, the physiological therapy approach is now seen as a traditional treatment. Few people confuse it with other forms of traditional medicine. Dietary medicine is one type, and it can take the form of anything from wood root to herbs and tablets. No less important than adding to the benefits of a full body massage is rubbing the problem area. It should be underlined that reflexologists never assume the responsibilities of physicians and that treatments including reflexology do not even touch the diseased parts of the body.

In many cases, there is a great deal of confusion about the use of tools to replace the thumb, especially the board. As a result, the therapy itself should not be too uncomfortable for the patient, as this may be an event that makes them reconsider seeking further treatment. The author places great emphasis on the use of one's hand throughout this book. In modern times, there are many diagrams showing the location of organ reflexes on the soles of the feet. It is common knowledge among many. However, it is essential to have in-depth knowledge of the human body, to be able to locate the body organs and to understand their functions. In addition, a full understanding of the nature of the disease and how it manifests in the body will make treatment more successful. This book begins with a brief introduction to body systems and then moves on to systematic massage techniques. In addition, there are lists with summary descriptions of diseases and reflexes that need to be categorized. Reflexology research based on scientific research is expected to continue in the future. They should be included as a subspecialty of physiotherapy in all hospitals and other types of medical facilities. New readers who are already familiar with the field of reflexology are advised to apply treatment modalities that do not cause side effects and can be applied at any time on their

own, such as foot massage itself. This is because these treatment methods are more likely to be effective. The author will be successful in convincing readers to use this strategy with their own family, friends and relatives. William H. Fitzgerald, a Swiss medical doctor of Swiss origin, on Therapy He is credited for introducing the reflex zone hypothesis through his book Zone . This was done from a reflexology perspective. 1917 was the year the book was first published. The therapy approach focused heavily on manual labor and made use of specific pieces of apparatus. On April 29, 1934, Fitzgerald was presented with a press release for his role in restoring the tone of a well-known performance artist.

7. Modern Time Reflexology

Even in modern times, people continue to learn about the longitudinal regions of their feet and hands, which are the areas associated with organs located in the same region. Practitioners can use this visual map to find the reflections of their organs on the feet and hands of their patients. This awareness was first introduced by Dr. Designed by William H. FitzGerald . This idea is called *Zone Theory* and serves as the foundation of contemporary reflexology.

Dr. Shelby Riley , Dr. He shows that after working closely with FitzGerald and learning the concept of longitudinal zones, he added horizontal zones along the hands and feet. Dr. FitzGerald noticed that when working on specific sites on his patients' toes and hands, they were able to withstand minor operations on their noses and throats without the need for anesthesia. By always observing how his patients experienced the procedures, he couldn't help but realize that from the procedures not only was pain relief, but also addressing the primary cause. This led him to conclude that the procedures were effective in treating both the symptoms and the underlying cause. When Bowers sees these results, Everyone's Magazine's editor Bruce Barton , Dr. He strongly encouraged FitzGerald to write and publish an article on Zone Therapy. Bruce Barton thought that no one would be interested in reading about it, which is common when new discoveries are made. He went so far as to assume that no one would believe there was any improvement result.

8. Conclusion

Teaching for the theory session covers topics such as the principle of reflexology, the physiological effect of reflexology, various reflex points of the feet, map theory, zones and cross reflexes, the relationship of reflex points with body organs, the use of reflexology for health. On the other hand, teaching for the hands-on session includes good hygiene practices and arranging treatment sessions, practicality of treatment, evaluation and documentation of the client's treatment, consultation, as well as methods of examining the client's feet. ("Revisiting reflexology: Concept, evidence, current practice, and ...") ("Revisiting reflexology: Concept, evidence, current practice, and ...") Much more work is needed in the literature on this subject.

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